

Symbiosis Of Learning: Music Education As An Integrator Of University Disciplines

Ojukwu, Ebele V. (Ph. D.).

Department of Music
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka Anambra State, Nigeria
ev.ojukwu@unzik.edu.ng
+(234)08037244058,

Abstract

The idea of the word ‘university’ emerged due to the desire to integrate all academic cultures. However, there seems to be an emerging trend of dichotomy between various disciplines and departments in the university which is beginning to brew toxic competition. Music education is fundamental to the very existence of human beings and it is one discipline that is particularly making connections across other disciplines. This qualitative paper is directed to the task of calling attention to the need to capture the symbiotic relationship among disciplines in the university system using music education as a case study to establish that within the uniqueness of every discipline, there exists a connectedness to various other disciplines, which embodies the original conception of university learning. Through library search, this study x-rays the scholastic component of the structural content of music education and its relationship to other disciplines in the university. Hinging this study on Greece’s philosophical views of university education, a solution for more collaboration between various disciplines in the university was proffered.

Keywords: Music education, University education, Academic culture and Symbiotic relationship.

Introduction

In the genesis of university education, it is presumed that the scholastic components of the university structural contents should constitute the two dominant fields in the university – Artistic/Humanistic studies and Science/technology – and should capture the symbiotic relationship. The university should be

conceived, as a citadel of learning where the culture of teaching, learning and research under an advisor should result in the cultivation of the intellect and knowledge gain through critical thinking. A university professor is professionally a principal expositor of a system that provides a forum for public policy debate, which in turn leads to a better informed audience (Fahm,

1978). The university has been characterized as an institution for scholars and students to facilitate debate and knowledge transfer; a place to develop the ability to analyze situations wisely, with a capacity to weigh the implication of actions and; a place to develop matured convictions and gaiety of mind, intellectual passion and search for essence all geared towards achieving academic freedom. In the university, various forms of interferences abound resulting in conflicts which if not properly handled may hinder academic freedom. In the words of Sanda (1992), academic freedom connotes:

Freedom to organize the university, design and teach courses, associate with others, project, imbibe, exchange and hold ideas without any fear of harassment or victimization, and challenge established orthodoxies without any fear of contradiction, all in the pursuit of truth (p.43).

In university administration, various units have to be synchronized for the goal of quality education to be attained (Sanda, 1992). These units include finance, academic programme, personnel, welfare, reward system and physical facilities. Any significant lapse in any of these units might lead to crisis. The goal of university education is pursued through its main functions and activities of teaching, research,

dissemination of existing and new information, service to the community, and being a storehouse of knowledge (FRN, 1981). In carrying out these functions, there are always conflicts within and among the various disciplines within the university community. Conflicts ranging from admission quota, project funding, research sponsorship, space allocation and appointments to clashes of personality abound in the university. Conflicts may also come from: students, academics, administrators, non-academics and their unions. Potentials for conflicts are multifarious within the university system. Ejiogu (1990) perceived conflict as mutual hostility and all kinds of opposition or antagonistic interaction including disagreements or controversies about ideas, values, and ways of life. He identified major types of conflicts as:

- Conflict due to hierarchy of positions which include (a) subordinate conflict - between the boss and his subordinate (such as between lecturers and students); (b) super-ordinate conflict - between the administrator and an authority over him (e.g. Vice Chancellor and the Visitor); (c) lateral conflict - between an administrator and his peer (e.g. between Vice Chancellors of two universities);
- Conflict based on the relationship between the objective state of affairs and the perceived state of affairs by conflicting parties (this conflict

could be veridical, contingent, displaced, misattributed or latent); and

- Conflicts based on antagonistic source such as conflict between cultural values and institutional expectations, role expectation and personality roles, and deriving from personality discord.

Alabi (2002) carried out a study on conflicts in Nigerian universities and identified conflict situations in various Nigerian universities from 1995 to 2001. According to Alabi “a conflict situation is characterized by the inability of those concerned to iron out their differences and reach an agreement on issues of common interest. These inabilities manifest in one form of protest or the other such as strikes and other work-disruptions (slow-downs, sabotage and planned absenteeism)”. University conflicts are summed up in the words of Olaleye & Arogundade (2003) thus:

Internally, university life is shaped by many logic, habits and dynamics. It is also influenced by various challenges, constraints and pressures from the outer environment. The combinations of external pressures and internal pressures within the university systems made administration very difficult and complex, therefore conflict is inevitable (p.97).

This paper is directed to the task of calling attention to the need to resolve conflicts and

cultivate the intellect in a way that exploits the symbiotic relationship among disciplines, and also maintain the original aim of university education. Music education is a major discipline that particularly makes connections across other disciplines and the purpose of this paper is to explore connections between music education and other university disciplines in order to establish that within the uniqueness of every discipline, there exists a symbiotic relationship with other disciplines. This paper also suggests that it is only by restoring harmony and shared purpose between disciplines, that the university will maximize its contribution to the society.

Greece’s Philosophical View of University Education

Historically, the concept of the university was developed with the establishment of ‘the Academy’ by Plato in the Olive groves of *Academicus* in Athens (Greece) in the 4th Century B. C. The pre-Socratics, kept wondering about the ultimate constitution of the universe, about the ultimate nature of things and so many other things making Plato and Aristotle to reason that the best way to immortalize the intellectual curiosities and wonders of the Athenians was to create an institution that formalizes and integrates all forms of knowledge. This was how the great academies, lyceums and universities started developing. In the academy, Plato taught

courses in all branches of philosophy including mathematics and studies of natural phenomena, “using observation and deductive reasoning as tools of analysis” (Ajayi, 2001& Osuntokun, 2006).

However, the culture of debate and critical enquiry amongst the Greeks started with curiosity and wonder about natural and social phenomena and about the meaning of concepts. This later culminated in the birth of ‘the Academy’ and ‘the lyceum’, institutions in Ancient Greece which were historically acknowledged as precursors of modern universities. The primary responsibility of the university to itself then, is the fostering of a true tradition of intellect. The university became a place where the individual man can synthesize new ideas, where the accident of friendship and association can open a man’s eyes to a part of human life remote and perhaps superficially incompatible. The foundation of this tradition is understanding of what the essence of life is. The quest for understanding requires systematic explorations, which are centralized where learned individuals gather — that is, in citadels of learning which are, by virtue of their tradition, open communities (Fahm:1978).

The idea of symbiotic learning calls for more integration among various disciplines in the university. It does not mean that schools should

avoid defining disciplines clearly; rather, they also need to create learning experiences that periodically demonstrate the relationship of the disciplines. University education is like a body which subdivides into several other smaller bodies. Ibekwe (2009) posits that “no aspect of this composite (body) can solely function effectively without relating or borrowing from the others for better output” (p.181). Nweke, 2018 also highlights that tertiary education has one of its objectives as training of man in the best means, to employ his ideas in action, and also to cultivate the necessary values in individuals that help them to model their lives properly.

Music as an Integrator of Disciplines

Music is an integral part of culture in any society and its scope and purpose is multidimensional. Its universality manifests in many settings and includes many different kinds of actions and ways of organizing sound into meanings. Glennon (1980) defines music as “organized movement of sound through a continuum of time” (p. 2). Music not only integrates people, it also integrates various disciplines and aids understanding of other disciplines. Ukpanah (2004) posits that “music helps to stimulate the brain and discipline the mind thereby serving as incentive for learning of other subjects” (p.21). In support of the above assertion Geraghty (2007) points out:

The point of contact between music and other subjects can give pupils the opportunity to choose their own personal route to knowledge of music. The subject can also serve as a concrete starting point and support for learning in other subjects, as well as for attaining the overall goals of the school. The close relationship with languages supports the pupil's development of independent understanding, knowledge and skills in music. Music and language both build on audio-communication and have many elements in common. Music is also closely related to mathematics, since many of the subject's concepts, covering everything from timing to keys and chords, are mathematically defined.

[<https://gupea.ub.gu.se/bitstream/2077/3929/1/HT06-1190-24.pdf>]

Music education is an art discipline that integrates different disciplines especially in the university allowing students to see connections and relevance between various disciplines, thus forming a deeper understanding and appreciation for the subject matter. This symbiotic nature of learning involves a balanced approach to teaching and research by finding and making innate, mutually beneficial connections between music education and other academic disciplines.

It was reported from the program carried out in New York City in which music and art are implemented into the school curriculum to improve scholastic scores of children at all levels where children made use of rhythms to learn basic elements in mathematics, like fractions, and multiplications. The facilitator of the program Bard in Chukwu (2006) writes thus:

Music helps teach the precognitive skills. It gives the students the capacity to trust themselves by providing internal discipline through a highly repetitive structure..... On the whole, students' feeling of self-confidence and accomplishment are great and most importantly, the students' attitude toward math and learning is increased dramatically (p. 25).

Music Education Integrating Artistic / Humanistic studies and Science / technology

Music education is a discipline in humanities and as such, it supports the need for education in the arts, culture and the humanities. As part of the humanities, music is capable of shaping the future being a source of what is true, beautiful and good, if it is allowed to exist in one's world view. Our philosophy, values, emotions and ethics can all be understood in the music that we create. It is precisely because of this depth that music is able to flow freely from the inside to the outside, from person to society, from the self to the non-self. Music can stimulate meaningful social interactions. This is because it enables

communication, beyond what is verbal, by inciting shared emotional responses. As a result, it supports the creation or enlargement of group identity: commonality versus uniqueness, togetherness versus aloneness, and collective feeling versus individuality. It can promote right behavior in vulnerable groups. In fact, music can be so effective in delivering such outcomes that in some places, its use is regulated by those in authority. Music stands for connectedness – the way notes are put together in a manner that is graceful, and the way harmony leads to something beautiful. Certainly, we can learn so much from it (Gisela, 2015).

In science and technological disciplines, music education can also be used to improve students' analytical and critical thinking skills. According to Chandler (2008) "all music emerge from the principles found in physics and math. In fact, centuries ago, some academics considered the study of music to be a kind of science. It was regarded as an important discipline alongside mathematics, geometry and astronomy". The most famous physicist of all time, Einstein was a passionate musician. Einstein's obsession for music was summarized in the Financial Times (2018) thus: whenever Einstein felt he had come to the end of the road or into a difficult situation in his work, he would take refuge in music and that would usually

resolve all his difficulties. Einstein was obsessed with composers such as Bach and Mozart. Even JS Bach, whose sublime music is often held up as the pinnacle of mathematical and scientific perfection, may not have been conscious of the patterns he was sequencing. To many contemporary musicians, the reliance on science is conscious rather than intuitive. The relationship between music technology and physics is "symbiotic". Major classical composers employ something akin to the "scientific method" to create their tunes [<https://www.ft.com/content/5a8ff636-36be-11e3-8ae3-00144feab7de> Financial Times (2018)

McNealy (2003) succinctly infers that the creative processes in musical art and science have much in common; music is the source of all true art and all science. According to him, Albert Einstein recognized that both science and art delve into the mysterious by stating that the most beautiful thing we can experience is the mysterious. McNealy is of the opinion that connecting these subjects in the minds of students will help them realize the importance of technology, industry, and progress in science and simultaneously emphasize the importance of art, music, and the humanities. "The tools presented here will encourage students to connect new science information through the

music and art they already know and, therefore, provide increased engagement and retention of the new knowledge” (p.267). Ibekwe (2009) also submits that advancement in technology and media services in the area of the arts has provided a big boost for optimized creativity in the construction of musical equipment and the mode of documenting music through electronic gadgets in a most refined way due to improved resources and artifacts.

Symbiosis of Music Education and other Disciplines

Music education is all encompassing and has come a long way in history and application as one of the artistic and humanistic studies (liberal studies) that dominated the Greek education. Unah (2008) opines that:

Liberal orientation rekindles human curiosity and inquisitiveness, which animate the spirit of inquiry and creativity. This is why the sciences and the humanities were originally united in the activities of early Greek thinkers, and the offerings of the university. [https://files.eric.ed.gov]

Music education cuts across broad areas and depicts the nexus that informs all human thoughts, ideas, and experiences. It touches on the length and breadth of virtually all disciplines ranging from disciplines in humanities to sciences. These various disciplines which are to

be discussed as distinct entities are a culmination of related ideas linked by the creative imagination (Ibekwe, 2009). Music is linked to learning, and humans have a strong pedagogical predilection. Learning not only takes place in the development of direct musical skills, but in the connections between music and other emotional experiences. Musical knowledge makes for a balanced and principled life and therefore, an indispensable aspect of several disciplines in the university education.

Mathematics and Music

Music is highly related to mathematics. Elementary mathematics is crucial to understanding of many concepts in music. Such concepts as kinds of scale (pentatonic, hexatonic, heptatonic), musical notes, shapes, values, intervals, tones and semitones, etc cannot be easily understood without elementary knowledge of mathematics. Kells (2010) avers thus:

Numbers, patterns, proportions, and ratios are just some of the concepts that are mastered by both mathematicians and musicians. Great thinkers from ancient times to the present have seen and used these conceptual links. For example, Pythagoras, the Greek mathematician, used math to make sense of musical concepts as he developed his ideas on music theory. Boethius, the Middle Age music expert,

articulated some of his musical ideas using math concepts. And who hasn't heard about Einstein's great love of music, which he said was extraordinarily helpful to him in his work? [<http://www.susi-up.de/wp-content/uploads/2010/04/ImpactOfMusicOnMath.pdf>]

Gardiner (2000) explicitly explores more specific early mathematics concepts that tie to music, including a "pitch line" similar to a number line. He believes that "mental stretching" can occur in children when music-math links are recognized and exploited. His multiple research studies have shown promising connections between progress in pitch and rhythm and progress in mathematics.

Languages / Literature and Music

Neurologists have found that music and language processing occur in the same area of the brain, and that there appear to be parallels in how musical and linguistic syntax is processed. Hence, music can be used as a promising instructional instrument in educational contexts. Addo & Potgieter (2003) affirm that "the relationship between music and language not only affects the mode of performance, but also contributes to the distinctive characteristics of a singing style and its harmony" (p.239). Several theoretical accounts proposed that, particularly

during early language acquisition, language is rather perceived as music (Mohammad & Rahim, 2016). Both are based on acoustic information, involving a limited number of categorical elements or classes (phonemes and tones) that are organized in structured sequences according to specific regularities. These regularities are acquired using similar learning mechanisms (McMullen & Saffran, 2004). Even on a very basic level, music and language are similar in that they are all compositional. This means that they are made of small parts that combine to make something larger and more meaningful. They involve the same areas of the brain. Research has shown that musical training can improve language skills. A study that was conducted to examine the relationship between development of music skills and language skills found out that the children who receive music lessons ended up with higher levels of phonological awareness than those who did not. According to Tucker (1981):
Using music as a tool for the teaching of reading not only secures music in the curriculum but may enhance the outcomes of reading instruction. The use of music with older students, even college students, as a tool for enhancing reading ability, is not as well documented, mainly because of

the scarcity of research fusing music and reading beyond the primary grade. (p. 16)

Music has the privilege of enabling a child not only to acquire the musical conceptions of his/her native culture but also enables him/her to acquire his/her native language. Ibekwe (2009) argues that “a good singer is known by the way he verbalizes his word and how eloquent and conversant he is with the proverbs, idioms and riddles of his community” (p. 186). Most Nigeria languages are tonal, and good musicologists and composers put into consideration the tonal inflections of these languages while composing. Onwuekwe (2004) shares the above view thus: “We have different languages in Nigeria and these languages obey or adhere to the tonal inflections of the word in spontaneous, indigenous or composed music of a particular culture. In all these music, be it Hausa, Yoruba, Igbo, Efik, etc music, there is unity in diversity” (p. 33). It is often said that music is the universal language of mankind. Indeed, music has great expressive power and manages to convey a vast array of sentiments and emotions even without the use of words. On both a descriptive and neutral level, language and music have a lot in common. Schulkin & Raglan (2014). Write thus:

Music is a fundamental part of our evolution; we probably sang before we spoke in syntactically

guided sentences. Song is represented across animal worlds; birds and whales produce sounds, though not always melodic to our ears, but still rich in semantically communicative functions. Song is not surprisingly tied to a vast array of semiotics that pervade nature: calling attention to oneself, expanding oneself, selling oneself, deceiving others, reaching out to others and calling on others. The creative capability so inherent in music is a unique human trait. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fnins.2014.00292/full>.

Music deals with lyrics, poem and rhyme. A composer must be good in the construction of good poems. Even when given a poem with many stanzas, a musicologist must scan it to make it rhyme before setting the time signature, otherwise the time of the music will be quite irregular. According to Mohammed & Rahim (2016) “Children are drawn to nursery rhymes, rhythmic activities, and songs as key texts in building concepts of reality” [<http://www.katibenovin.com>]. Most children can easily remember rhyme, poem, rhythm and melody more than mere speech. This is in line with Wallace (1994), when comparing recall ability, found that spoken text was the least frequently recalled, followed by rhyming text, and then with melodic text as the easiest to remember. Wallace compared immediate and

long-term recall of spoken texts to texts learned with music. Results of the study indicated that recall was significantly greater for the music condition than for the spoken condition, revealing that “music, when repeated, simple, and easily learned can make a text more easily learned and better recalled than when the same text is learned without any melody” (pp. 1473-1474).

Physics and Music

In many ways music and physics have a symbiotic relationship. Wavelengths are the medium through which music is measured in physics. From the lenses of physics, music is varying sound waves that create measurable patterns. The art of tuning a musical instrument is directly related to physics. The acoustics of music is pure physics. A student of music needs a good knowledge of physics to understand how to deal with sound during performances, both indoor and outdoor performances. Doyle in Ortivestm (2011) explains that when a tone is reverberated simultaneously with another tone, it will create separate wavelength patterns that can be graphed. If those patterns do not match up or overlap on the graph, then that signifies the tones are not in tune. Basically, if the tones give off a “beating” sound that rises and falls, then those sounds are out of tune. As Doyle described the musical aspects of physics, she focused on the

idea of harmonics and scales which both relate to the frequency of a wave. Western music has sought to find the harmony of the frequency according to physics, in order to make the best sounding scales possible. Through the study of frequency, harmonics was discovered which lead to the formation of scales that date back to the early Greek philosophers.

Psychology and Music

Music is social in nature; the social value of reaching others in music or by moving others through a song across the broad social milieu is inherently felt. Music may very well be one of those universal truths that foster connections and propel them forward. When we disclose our favorite songs, or musical pieces that affect us in some capacity, we could be giving others a glimpse into who we are as individuals. We identify with particular lyrical narratives and emotional dispositions and beautiful melodies, sharing pieces of ourselves in the process. As a music composer or performer, knowledge of psychology is required to be able to interpret any music before a given audience. A musicologist must understand the psychological state of the audience before whom he/she is performing otherwise negative impression could be created or the performance misinterpreted.

Music education has so much to do with psychology to the extent that a whole course in the university is dedicated to psychology named “music psychology” and within this course; connections between music and psychological issues are explored. Hodges (2003) gave a highlight of underpinnings in music psychology and infers:

Music psychology is a multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary study of the phenomenon of music. The multidisciplinary nature of the field is found in explorations of the anthropology of music, the sociology of music, the biology of music, the physics of music, the philosophy of music, and the psychology of music. Interdisciplinary aspects are found in such combinatorial studies as psychoacoustics (e.g., music perception), psychobiology (e.g., the effects of music on the immune system), or social psychology (e.g., the role of music in social relationships) (p. 31).

Theatre and Music

Music and theatre are like twin sisters; one cannot do without the other to the extent that in some universities, music and theatre are merged into one department named performing arts. The performing arts range from vocal and instrumental music, dance and theatre to pantomime, sung verse and beyond. They include numerous cultural expressions that reflect human creativity and that are also found,

to some extent, in many other intangible cultural heritage domains. Ibekwe (2009) asserts: “The relationship between music and drama as elements of theatre becomes more glaring when terms as musical ‘theatre’, ‘music drama’, ‘opera’, ‘dance drama’, ‘vaudeville’ or ‘variety show’, ‘masque’ and ‘total theatre are discussed” (p. 185). UNESCO (2017) writing on performing arts further declares:

Music is perhaps the most universal of the performing arts and is found in every society, most often as an integral part of other performing art forms and other domains of intangible cultural heritage including rituals, festive events or oral traditions. It can be found in the most diverse contexts: sacred or profane, classical or popular, closely connected to work or entertainment.

[<https://ich.unesco.org/en/performing-arts-00054>]

Geography/History and Music

Musicologists study music of other world cultures. This exposes the students of music to the history, geographical location, background, culture, religion, occupation, etc of other world cultures in order to perform the music from every part of the world to a reasonable standard. It also enables musicologists to be aware of the climate of various places of the world and what constitute the type of musical performances and

instruments produced in such geographical locations. This is why many musicologists can easily detect the geographical origin of any music by merely listening to few samples even for a very first time. Mohammad & Rahim, 2016 point out:

Music helps connect people with new cultures and opens up a whole new world, just one of the reasons why songs are an important element of teaching world languages. There are an infinite number of songs that discuss culturally relevant topics, such as human relations, ethics, customs, history and humor, as well as regional and cultural differences. These songs can help teach language and culture simultaneously.

(<http://www.katibenovin.com>)

Religion and Music

Music helps form the basics of all religious groups – be it Christian, Islamic or the African traditional religion. All religions use music for various forms of rituals and for souls' upliftment in their various churches, temples, mosques, shrines. Musicologists requires knowledge of different kinds of music as they relate to all religions since many religions only approve of certain kinds of music while strictly forbidding all others. Some religions also limit the use of certain kinds of music to very specific occasions, seasons or time periods. Obicheta (2013)

remarks that initiation music is for initiating young boys into the masquerade cult while *Iru Mgbede* (fattening room) is reserved for young maidens in certain areas of Nigeria. Divination music can only be performed by herbalists, soothsayers or fortune tellers to appease their gods so that they can send messages to them. Religious ministers and evangelists also make heavy use of music to spread the word of God and gain converts.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This paper has tried to argue that neither the arts/humanities education nor the scientific /technological education can exclusively guarantee the well being of mankind's happiness and that the symbiotic nature of all disciplines should be acknowledged and respected. From the foregoing discussion, it is evident that symbiotic learning is a strategy for dealing with institutional knowledge and learning challenges and also a means of curtailing the negative consequences of conflicts; hence it enables knowledge generation to become increasingly relocated from segregated and specialized institution. This curtailment of conflicts could be achieved through meaningful interactions and effective communication; resourcefulness and resource management; and cooperation among the university staff. All these measures would

culminate in drastic reduction in negative conflict potentials and consequent high goal attainment potential.

There is a need to actively show students how different subject areas influence their lives, and it is critical that students see the strength of each discipline. The paper captured the symbiotic relationship between music and many other disciplines while x-raying the scholastic component of the university and structural content of the music and other disciplines. It highlighted what is considered to be the relationship between music and other disciplines which ought to elicit fair treatment in the universities. This in the long run will make people to act thoughtfully and responsibly.

If more effort is geared towards interdisciplinary studies in the universities, in time, staff and students will see for themselves how things fit together. The reality of the situation is that students tend to learn what the lecturers teach. If they teach connectedness and integration, they learn that but if they teach separation and discontinuity, that is what students learn.

References

Addo, A. O., Miya, F. & Potgieter, H. (2003). In A. Herbst, M. Nzewi and K. Agawu. (Eds.). *Integrating the arts. Musical Arts*

in Africa: Theory, Practices and Education. (pp. 236 – 260). Pretoria: Unisa Press.

Alabi, A. T. (2002). Conflicts in Nigerian universities: Causes and management. *Ilorin Journal of Education (IJE)*, 21, afusatalabi.com. Retrieved: 16th May, 2018.

Ajayi, J. F. A. (2001). Development is about people. In A. Banjo (Ed.). *Humanity in Context.* (pp.56-68) Ibadan: The Nigerian Academy of Letters.

Chandler, N. (2008). *10 Connections between physics and music.* Available @ [<https://entertainment.howstuffworks.com/10-connections-physics-music.htm>] Retrieved: 16th May, 2018.

Chukwu, S. K. I. (2006). The influence of background music on children's learning. *Awka Journal of Research in Music and the Arts (AJRMA)*, 3, 19-31

Ejiogu, A. M. (1990). *Educational management: A system approach.* Lagos: Lantern books.

Fahm, L. A. (1978). The responsibility of the university to itself. *African Insight*; 4 (1), 98-109.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (1981). *National policy on education* Lagos: NERDC.

Financial Times (2008). *The sounds of science: How physics and music can help each other.* Available @ [<https://www.ft.com/content/5a8ff636-36be-11e3-8ae3-00144feab7de>]. Retrieved: 19th May, 2018.

Gardiner, M. F. (2000). Music, learning and behavior: A case for mental stretching. *Journal for Learning through Music*, 1, 72-93.

- Geraghty, J. (2007). Music in an integrated curriculum – why doesn't everybody do it. [<https://gupea.ub.gu.se/bitstream/2077/3929/1/HT06-1190-24.pdf>] Retrieved 19th July. 2018
- Gisela, P. (2015). *Music, humanities and a globalized society*. Available @ [<http://ovpaa.up.edu>], Retrieved: 16th May, 2018.
- Glennon, J. (1980). *Understanding music*. London: Macmillian.
- Hodges, D. A. (2003). Music education and music psychology: What's the connection. *Research Studies in Music Education*, 21, 31-44.
- Ibekwe, E. U. (2009). Artistic integration: The centrality of music. *AMA: Journal of Theatre and Cultural Studies*, 4, (1), 181-191.
- Kells, D. (2010). *The impact of music on mathematics achievement*. Available @ [<http://www.susi-up.de/wp-content/uploads/2010/04/ImpactOfMusicOnMath.pdf>] Retrieved: 09th August, 2018.
- Mohammad, S. K. & Rahim, F. (2016). *Music and language learning*. Available @ [<http://www.katibenovin.com>] Retrieved: 16th May, 2018.
- McMullen E. & Saffran J. R. (2004). Music and language: A developmental comparison. *Music Percept*, 21, 289-311.
- McNealy, T.L. (2003). Connecting music, art and science for increased creativity and topic enlargement. *Journal of Microbiology and Biology Education*, 14 (2), 267-268.
- Nweke, P. C. (2018). Going back to the root. *The Thinker: Scientia Est Potentia* 26, 3-6.
- Obicheta, J. C. (2013). *Graded music for senior secondary schools and colleges*. Onitsha: Jenison Publishing Company.
- Olaleye, F. O & Arogundade, B. B. (2003). Conflict management strategies of university administrators in South-West Nigeria. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*. 2, (6), 96-104
- Onwuekwe. A. I. (2004). The interrelationship of Nigerian music with the other arts. *Awka Journal of Research in Music and the Arts (AJRMA)*, 2, 31-40.
- Ortivistm, N. C. (2011). *The mutual harmony between music and physics*. Available @ [<https://blogs.adams.edu/thepawprint/the-mutual-harmony-between-music-and-physics/>]. Retrieved: 16/5/18
- Osuntokun, A. (2006). *Incipient Exit of Town and Gown from the Ivory Tower*. Lagos: First Academic Publishers.
- Sanda, O. A. (1992). *Managing Nigerian universities*. Ibadan: spectrum.
- Schulkin & Raglan (2014). *Evolution of music and human social capability*. Available @ [<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fnins.2014.00292/full>]. Retrieved: 16/5/18
- Tucker, A. (1981). Music and the teaching of reading: A review of the literature. *Reading Improvement*, 18, 14-19.
- Ukpanah, I. D. (2004). Music education as a vehicle of national orientation. *Awka Journal of Research in Music and the Arts (AJRMA)*, 2, 21-30.

Unah, J. I. (2008). *The symbiotic relationship between liberal studies and science*. Available @ [<http://files.eric.ed.gov>]. Retrieved: 16/5/18

UNESCO (2017). *Performing arts*. Available @ [<https://ich.unesco.org/en/performing-arts-00054>] Retrieved: 16th May, 2018.

Wallace, W. (1994). Memory for music: Effect of melody on recall of text. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, 20 (6), 1471-1485.